

CLINICAL ANATOMY OF THE SPINE AND SPINAL CORD

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Annotation. Dear colleagues, the material offered to you was once prepared by the author for the chapter of the manual on neuraxial anesthesia, which, for a number of reasons, was not completed and was not published. We believe that the information presented below will be of interest not only to novice anesthesiologists, but also to experienced specialists, since it reflects the most modern ideas about the anatomy of the spine, epidural and subarachnoid spaces from the point of view of an anesthesiologist.

Anatomy of the spine

As you know, the spinal column consists of 7 cervical, 12 thoracic and 5 lumbar vertebrae with the adjacent sacrum and coccyx. It has several clinically significant bends. The greatest bends anteriorly (lordosis) are located at the C5 and L4–5 levels, and posteriorly at the Th5 and S5 levels. These anatomical features, together with the baricity of local anesthetics, play an important role in the segmental distribution of the level of spinal block.

The characteristics of individual vertebrae influence the technique, primarily of epidural puncture. The spinous processes extend at different angles at different levels of the spine. In the cervical and lumbar regions, they are located almost horizontally in relation to the plate, which facilitates median access when the needle is perpendicular to the axis of the spine. At the mid-thoracic level

(Th 5-9) the spinous processes extend at fairly acute angles, which makes the paramedian approach preferable. The processes of the upper thoracic (Th 1-4) and lower thoracic (Th 10-12) vertebrae are oriented intermediately compared to the two above features. At these levels, neither access has advantages over the other.

Access to the epidural (ED) and subarachnoid space (SP) is carried out between the plates (interlaminar). The superior and inferior articular processes form the facet joints, which play an important role in correctly positioning the patient before ED puncture. The correct positioning of the patient before ES puncture is determined by the orientation of the facet joints. Because the facet joints of the lumbar vertebrae are oriented in the sagittal plane and allow anterior-posterior flexion, maximum spinal flexion (fetal position) increases the interlaminar spaces between the lumbar vertebrae.

The facet joints of the thoracic vertebrae are oriented horizontally and provide rotational movements of the spine. Therefore, excessive spinal flexion does not provide additional benefit when performing EC puncture at the thoracic level.

Anatomical bony landmarks Identification of the required intervertebral space is the key to the success of epidural and spinal anesthesia, as well as a necessary condition for patient safety.

In a clinical setting, the choice of puncture level is made by the anesthesiologist through palpation in order to identify certain bony landmarks. It is known that the 7th cervical vertebra has the most pronounced spinous process. At the same time, it must be taken into account that in patients with scoliosis, the most protruding process may be the spinous process of the 1st thoracic vertebra (in approximately 1/3 of patients).

The line connecting the lower angles of the shoulder blades passes through the spinous process of the 7th thoracic vertebra, and the line connecting the iliac crests (Tuffier's line) passes through the 4th lumbar vertebra (L₄).

Identification of the required intervertebral space using bone landmarks is not always correct. The results of the study by Broadbent et al . (2000), in which one of the anesthesiologists used a marker to mark a certain intervertebral space at the lumbar level and tried to identify its level with the patient in a sitting position, the second made the same attempt with the patient in the lateral position. A contrast marker was then attached over the mark made and magnetic resonance imaging was performed. Most often, the true level at which the mark was made was one to four segments lower than the values reported by the anesthesiologists participating in the study. It was possible to correctly identify the intervertebral space only in 29% of cases. The accuracy of the determination did not depend on the patient's position, but worsened in overweight patients. By the way, the spinal cord ended at the L₁ level in only 19% of patients (in the rest at the L₂ level), which created a risk of damage to it if a high puncture level was incorrectly chosen. What makes it difficult to choose the correct intervertebral space?

There is evidence that Tuffier's line corresponds to level L₄ in only 35% of people (Reynolds F., 2000). For the remaining 65%, this line is located at the level from L₃₋₄ to L_{5-S1}.

It should be noted that an error of 1–2 segments when choosing the level of puncture of the epidural space, as a rule, does not affect the effectiveness of epidural anesthesia and analgesia.

Spinal ligaments

The anterior longitudinal ligament runs along the anterior surface of the vertebral bodies from the skull to the sacrum, which is rigidly fixed to the intervertebral discs and the edges of the vertebral bodies. The posterior longitudinal ligament connects the posterior surfaces of the vertebral bodies and forms the anterior wall of the spinal canal.

The vertebral plates are connected by the ligamentum flavum, and the posterior spinous processes by the interspinous ligaments. The supraspinous ligament runs along the outer surface of the spinous processes C₇ – S₁. The pedicles of the vertebrae are not connected by ligaments, resulting in the formation of intervertebral foramina through which the spinal nerves exit.

The ligamentum flavum consists of two layers fused along the midline at an acute angle. In this regard, it is, as it were, stretched in the form of an “awning”. In the cervical and thoracic regions, the ligamentum flavum may not be fused in the midline, causing problems in identifying ES using a loss of resistance test. The ligamentum flavum is thinner in the midline (2–3 mm) and thicker at the margins (5–6 mm). In general, it has the greatest thickness and density at the lumbar (5–6 mm) and thoracic levels (3–6 mm), and the smallest in the cervical region (1.5–3 mm). Together with the vertebral arches, the ligamentum flavum forms the posterior wall of the spinal canal.

When passing the needle through the median approach, it must pass through the supraspinous and interspinous ligaments, and then through the ligamentum flavum. With the paramedian approach, the needle bypasses the supraspinous and interspinous ligaments, immediately reaching the ligamentum flavum. The ligamentum flavum is denser than the others (80% consists of elastic fibers), therefore, an increase in resistance when passing it with a needle, followed by its loss, is known to be used to identify ES. The distance between the ligamentum flavum and the dura mater in the lumbar region does not exceed 5–6 mm and

depends on factors such as arterial and venous low pressure, pressure in the spinal canal, pressure in the abdominal cavity (pregnancy, abdominal compartment syndrome, etc.) and the chest cavity (ventilator).

With age, the ligamentum flavum thickens (ossifies), making it difficult to pass a needle through it. This process is most pronounced at the level of the lower thoracic segments.

Meninges of the Spinal Cord The spinal canal has three connective tissue membranes that protect the spinal cord: the dura mater, the arachnoid (arachnoid) membrane, and the pia mater. These membranes are involved in the formation of three spaces: epidural , subdural and subarachnoid. The spinal cord (SC) and roots are covered by a well- vascularized pia mater; the subarachnoid space is limited by two adjacent membranes - the arachnoid and dura mater.

All three SC sheaths continue in the lateral direction, forming the connective tissue covering of the spinal roots and mixed spinal nerves (endoneurium , perineurium and epineurium). The subarachnoid space also extends for a short distance along the roots and spinal nerves, ending at the level of the intervertebral foramina. In some cases, the cuffs formed by the dura mater extend by a centimeter or more (in rare cases by 6–7 cm) along the mixed spinal nerves and extend significantly beyond the intervertebral foramina. This fact must be taken into account when performing a brachial plexus block from supraclavicular approaches, since in these cases, even with the correct orientation of the needle, intrathecal administration of a local anesthetic is possible with the development of a total spinal block (this situation is described in more detail in our journal No. 4, 2007, p. 54 –56).

The dura mater (DRM) is a sheet of connective tissue consisting of collagen fibers oriented both transversely and longitudinally, as well as a certain amount of elastic fibers oriented in the longitudinal direction.

For a long time , it was believed that TMO fibers have a predominantly longitudinal orientation. In this regard, it was recommended that when puncturing the subarachnoid space, the cut of the spinal needle with the cutting tip should be oriented vertically so that it does not cross the fibers, but rather pushes them apart. Later, using electron microscopy, a rather random arrangement of dura fibers was revealed - longitudinal, transverse and partially circular. The thickness of the dura mater is variable (from 0.5 to 2 mm) and may differ at different levels in the same patient. The thicker the dura mater, the higher its ability to retract (constrict) the defect.

The dura mater, the thickest of all SC membranes, has long been considered as the most significant barrier between the EP and the underlying tissues. In reality this is not the case. Experimental studies with morphine and alfentanil performed on animals showed that the dura mater is the most permeable membrane of the SC (Bernardis C., Hill H., 1990).

A false conclusion about the leading barrier function of the dura mater on the diffusion path has led to an incorrect interpretation of its role in the genesis of post-puncture headache (PDPH). If we assume that PDPH is caused by a leak of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) through a puncture defect in the membranes of the spinal cord, we must correctly conclude which of them is responsible for this leak. Since the CSF is located under the arachnoid membrane, it is the defect of this membrane, and not the dura mater, that plays a role in the mechanisms of PDPH. Currently, there is no evidence indicating that it is the defect in the membranes of the

spinal cord, and therefore its shape and size, as well as the rate of CSF loss (and therefore the size and shape of the needle tip) that influence the development of PDPH.

This does not mean that the clinical observations showing that the use of thin needles, pencil-point needles, and the vertical orientation of the cut of Quincke-type needles reduce the incidence of PDPH are incorrect. However, explanations for this effect are incorrect, in particular, statements that when the cut is vertically oriented, the needle does not intersect the dura mater fibers, but “spreads” them apart. These statements completely ignore modern understanding of the anatomy of the dura mater, which consists of randomly arranged fibers, rather than oriented vertically. At the same time, the cells of the arachnoid membrane have a cephalo-caudal orientation (see below). In this regard, when the cut is oriented longitudinally, the needle leaves a narrow slit-like hole in it, damaging fewer cells than when oriented perpendicularly. However, this is only an assumption that requires serious experimental confirmation.

Correct understanding of the anatomy of the spine and the structures of the spinal canal is absolutely necessary in the daily practice of an anesthesiologist-resuscitator. They are the key to the success of neuraxial blockades, and also help to minimize the number of complications of neuraxial anesthesia, which are sometimes life-threatening.

References:

1. Angst M., Ramaswamy B., Riley E., Stanski D. Lumbar epidural morphine in humans and supraspinal analgesia to experimental heat pain // *Anesthesiology* . 2000; 92: 312–324.
2. Bernards C., Hill H. Physical and chemical properties of drug molecules governing their diffusion through the spinal meninges. // *Anesthesiology* . 1992; 77: 750–756.
3. Bernards S., Sorkin L. Radicular artery blood flow does not redistribute fentanyl from epidural space to the spinal cord // *Anesthesiology* . 1994; V: 872–878.
4. Broadbent C., Maxwell W., Ferrie R. Ability of anesthesia to identify a marked lumbar interspace // *Anaesthesia*. 2000; 55:1045–1046.
5. Carpenter R., Hogan Q., Liu S. Lumbosacral cerebrospinal fluid volume is the primary determinant of sensory block extent and duration during spinal anesthesia . // *Anesthesiol* . 1998; 89: 24–29.
6. Cousins M., Bridenbaugh P. *Neural Blockade in Clinical Anesthesia and Management of Pain*, 3rd ed., Philadelphia:
7. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins , 1998.